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The Historical Aspects Of ‘Translation’ (Anuvādam) - An Overview

Dr. Sajeesh C S ¹

Abstract

Translation is essential in today’s world, bridging cultural and linguistic divides. It allows the sharing of knowledge and fosters understanding. Modern technology enhances its significance, enabling quick access to information globally. Translation is a powerful communication tool, uniting people and promoting national integration. It plays a vital role in various fields like education, media, and administration. Effective translation must balance beauty and faithfulness, ensuring the text’s reliability and aesthetic appeal. The discipline of translation has evolved, highlighting its crucial role in the interconnected, technologically advanced era we live in.

Keywords- Art, Communication, Language, Literature, Process, Science, Translation,

Introduction

The translation is a very most observable process. It is possible to establish every culture in the world through systematic work of translations. The translation has not emerged recently it has a long tradition. Translation is as old as humanity (1). The process of translation takes place in different ways based on the needs of humans. The study of translation begins in the first century BC (1). Albeit very recently it is considered as an academic discipline. The translation is mostly studied in comparative literature and contrastive linguistics. Moreover, it is used as a teaching tool in language studies. The

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possibilities of translation studies have increased rapidly nowadays. So many scholars have recognized the likelihood of translation and they have done it to develop academic discourses. They have tried to bring out several theories and systemically applied them into translation study. Translation is an essential process in the present scenario. Beyond understanding all matters in the world, it helps to obtain deep knowledge of that particular subject. So, it is considered a worldwide process. Later it becomes a separate popular theory or discipline in the field of academic study centers.

Translation developed a separate branch regarding applied linguistics where the discipline was known by different names by different scholars such as science of translation, translatology, and translation Studies (1). Though the development of this discipline firstly in the literary field some aspects also diffused into nonliterary like dubbing and sub-titling.

In ancient India, the translation first started with religious texts, especially in Sanskrit texts. Today it is widely expanded with many fields like newspaper, Sahitya Academy, banking, law, technical, and administrative areas. With that many avenues like machine translation are opened up through the translation.

Definitions of Translation

Different scholars have tried to give an accurate definition of translation. The prefix of this word is trans which means going across. Transcendental, transcultural transnational, etc. are applied the synonyms of the word Translation.

Translation refers to studying the lexicon, grammatical structure communication situation, and cultural context of the source language text, analyzing it to determine its meaning, and then transferring or restructuring this same meaning using the appropriate lexicon, grammatical structure, and communication situation in the target or receptor language and its cultural context (4). The translation is like a beautiful woman. If beautiful, it cannot be faithful, and if faithful, it cannot be beautiful (19).

Translation is a multilayered and complex activity. Two languages must be needed for the translation process. One language is necessary

to translate into another language. So, the primary language is considered the parent language in the translation process, hence it is known as the source language. Another one is the target language which is being translated from original text. However, the translator must understand the two languages when translating the text. The action of translation is not easy which is created more complexity. The lack of total equivalence between the two cultures, incorrect sentences, and grammatical mistakes led to the wrong translation.

Translation as an Art

There have been many ways to determine the translation process. Some scholars say the translation is an art because the translation process in a literary work's poetic and aesthetic function is predominant. The translation of literature work by a translator must have required artistic ability with aesthetic sensibility and a different kind of sensitivity. Briefly, a translator should be a sense to distinguish complications as an artist. To some, translation is an art.

Translation as a Science

However, many attributes of the translation can be defined as a science. Because of these technical aspects are required. Translators have to change from the role of the artist to the scientist. The translation process is generally considered as the remaking of the message of language. Sometimes this is not a pure science-based activity. Whereas, scientific aspects need to derive the perfection of the translation through which will only get a good message to communicate that having in Source language. Language itself is a science. The discipline of linguistics is defined as the scientific study of language. The process of translation is scientific.

Historical Aspects of Translation

Behind the translation process or discipline laid down a huge history. Several ancient manuscripts and inscriptions have been discovered from time immemorial among them Rosetta² was the very ancient inscription in connection with translation. Some historians

2 "The Rosetta stone is a stele composed of granodiorite inscribed with three versions of a decree issued in Memphis, Egypt, in 196BC during the Ptolemaic dynasty on behalf of king Ptolemy Epiphanes. (Viswanathan E.A. 18)

argued that hieroglyphs³ and demotic⁴ languages were used in the Rosetta inscription which was very popular to reveal the mysteries around Egypt. Babylon was known as a multilingual city in B.C.2100 (Viswanathan P18) where collective writers tried to translate into various languages. They were expressed to have a schedule that embraced the synonyms of the words in different languages.

A specific translation method was developed in the Yehuda community at BC397 (Viswanathan). They could not be able to understand the content of the Hebrew⁵ language. Therefore, the translators used it in different ways. The Aramaic⁶ language was used in ancient times. Its main purpose is the interpretation of affairs which was the celebrated language. The diversity of the bible leads to a new thought and perspectives. The Bible was the most necessary text because of its content to understand to be done translation so it translated into the Greek language. It was possible to comprehend the wide aspects of human life by translating the bible into various languages. As part of the constrain Ecclesiastes and the old law of the bible were translated and the trend of translation diffused rapidly the whole world. Still, now the translation of the bible is continuously going on. Another movement of the translation stages was from the Greek to the Latin translation process and vice versa. Several texts have been translated at that time especially related to the religion. They had a wide knowledge of the system of nature.

The Arab countries have a vital role in the manner of translations. Bagdad was a state in Arab where had taken place various sophisticated knowledge of communication briefly it was a central gnostic. The Greek texts were constantly translated into the Arab language. Ancient Indian text was also translated into the Arabi language which paved the way to spread into other languages. Panchatantra

- 3 Egyptian hieroglyphs were the formal writing system used in ancient Egypt, used for writing the Egyptian language. Hieroglyphs combined logographic, syllabic, and alphabetic elements, with a total of some 1000 distinct characters
- 4 It is the ancient Egyptian script derived from northern forms of hieratic used in the Nile Delta, and the stage of the Egyptian language written in this script, following late Egyptian and preceding Coptic.
- 5 It is a northwest Semitic language of the Afroasiatic language family.
- 6 It was closely related to Hebrew, Syriac, and Phoenician and was written in a script derived from the Phoenician alphabet

was the most popular text in Sanskrit written by Vishnu Sarmma. He was an eminent poet in Sanskrit literature. This text was first translated into Arabic in the name of "Kalila damana" (Viswanathan 18). Later it was pervaded into other European languages. During the 9th century, several precious texts have been translated into different languages. King Alfred who ruled in England in the 9th century to propagate epistemological works did severe effort. He tried to translate more texts and promoted them to others. Some putative works have been translated into English by him.

After a long period of creating a wide knowledge becomes their responsibility. Hence the process of translation has been continued. At the beginning of the 13th century, several universities were established like Paris, Padua, Naples Oxford, etc. where the Greek and Latin texts were learned and given the most significant place. Archimedes and Galileo wrote many books in Greek and Latin.

Discoveries and the dimensions of universal truth are overdone to comprehend. They needed these translation works to understand the easy way. Translation work to some extent helpful to find more inventions. So, they are trying to translate several works. At the beginning of the modern era, many languages are snooping as a powerful tool to solve complicated communication. The new inventions of science were insisted to do the translation. As part of the growth of science in a new era, the translation of the texts helps to understand science theories. Without Translation, it would not be possible to understand the content and principles of science-based texts. Archimedes, Galileo, Gilvani, Marconi, Edison, Darvin, Lui Pasteur, and Mary Curie were notable personalities who made major contributions to the cognitive field.

The translation process was indispensable which is not only in science but also in arts and literature. It mostly helped the development of languages, especially on the account of political and administration texts. The English language was spread whole world. The main reason for translation is that the medium of communication of people is mostly in English so, many texts were translated into English from various languages. Almost all fields of epistemological texts have been translated. A summary of the texts was translated by various notable works and published under the title of Master

Pieces of World Literature. Among them, English works were more dominant rather than other languages.

At the same time, most of the works are also translated into the mother tongue or regional languages. The bible which was translated into English has been made an effort to do the translation into Malayalam. Many Greek texts were translated into Malayalam by using English translation.

Examining the translation process based on historical perspectives cannot be avoidable for the Indian translation fields and their pioneers. Because most of the works contributed to various Indian languages from English and Greek. There can be some specialties and differences from the European tradition in the manner of translation because Sanskrit was a prominent cultural language among the Indian languages. Sanskrit was a rigid language and it was used only by the higher people in society. Therefore, from the other languages to Sanskrit, the process of translation was taking place that was doubted. Notwithstanding some mathematical work that was written in Greek and translated into Sanskrit. Later the translation process of Sanskrit rapidly developed as part of this few epic texts were translated into Sanskrit. The translation of Tulsidas Ramayana was the best example of this.

Translation today has become a worldwide process where constantly several languages were taking place as continuously translated from one to another languages. In the Indian context, the translation process was accepted and it developed as a discipline in various universities rather than other abroad universities. In the account of Sanskrit, several translations especially Malayalam were produced. A huge effort has taken place for this from the various parts of India. The process of translation may be classified according to the regional languages. Each of them a has wide history.

Significance of Translation

Today the translation has diffused into various parts of the field of knowledge. Several theories also developed based on translation and it learnt various universalities as an academic discourse. Some academic subjects like Sanskrit and Malayalam included translation in their syllabus. Degree and postgraduate Sanskrit students are studying translation which leads to further studies and the interested

students may be selected and their career to be better in this field. Today computer translation also paves the way to an infinite possibility.

Translation can resolve social problems. It can bring people together, and give them a different sensitivity and sensibility to appreciate each other's viewpoints. Translation can remove the barriers to communication between two languages. It can safeguard against regionalism and can promote national integration. Ironically, in India, people are ignorant of their neighbors' mother tongue and its creativity. They are imprisoned in their world and refuse to acknowledge the beauty and richness of each other's culture. In the present scenario, the field of translation is most valuable. It has become widespread in the world because everywhere and every place needs a translation. The translation is now increasing with modern technology. The most powerful weapon to fight others is knowledge. With this knowledge, we can get more confidential power. Through the translation to be likely the discerning of the cultures and writing styles of authors. So, they are the major factors of translation. Moreover, it is possible to understand the lifestyle of human beings and their social-cultural activities in other countries. New ideas and stories from other regions can be understood through the translation. This may be any media like cinema, news, texts, etc. Anyway, any translation process only aims to understand the unity of the culture in others. After understanding the significance of translation, the study of translation has been approved by UGC in the present scenario. Authorities and other institutions are giving more benefits to translators. Not only Sanskrit books but every book published in any language. They have also translated from the source language to the target language. Therefore, the study of translation is indispensable. In the future, this study will be spread to every corner of the world. The necessity of translation is increasing every moment. So, it is considered an essential factor.

Conclusion

It does not make it possible to mark it correctly because there is no suitable or believed evidence to establish the history of the Translation. Some scholars believe that the translation period began after translating the Sanskrit text Bhagavad Gita. Who is the first

translator? Which is the first translated text? These two questions have no correct answer today. Some literary elements have to be known about the processing of the translation. To teach the text today all depend on the translation texts. Thus, every need of human action which is connected with translation is the most important role.

A translator should have a deep knowledge of source languages and target languages. It is a creative process of building bridges between languages and cultures (Viswanathan 10). He must have the deep knowledge to understand the basic differences between the two languages. Such as their unity also. So, the act of translation is not a mechanical one, it is a creative endeavor too. Technical terminology and good writing skills are crucial factors in the translation process. They are called two fundamental elements in the translation process. It is possible to understand the message to the public readers is the main purpose of translation. It helps the various knowledge extend to all over the world. The translation is a process that transfers the different cultural aspects of human life. So, it is said that translation is the best tool for communication in the globalization era. Every field in the world is governed by translation, especially in media. Exclusive news to report worldwide ultimately needs translation provided in different languages so many transliterators need to meet this process. Thus, translation gives a wide range of job opportunities. The study of translation gives more chances to students for jobs. Job facilities and opportunities are increasing day to day.

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